

Sports And Orthodontics - Protecting Smiles On The Field

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Introduction

Athletes, regardless of their discipline, are at a heightened risk of dental injuries due to the physical demands of their activities. Safeguarding their oral health is essential, not only for maintaining an attractive smile but also for promoting overall well-being, thus, enhancing their peak performance.¹

Sports-related oral injuries account for approximately 14% of all dental injuries, with an estimated five million teeth being damaged annually as a result of sports activities.² Contact sports, such as football, basketball, baseball, soccer, wrestling, hockey, ice hockey, and cricket characterized by direct physical interaction with other players or objects, pose a particularly high risk of trauma and injuries. Although non-contact yet high-risk sports, such as kung-fu, skiing, mountain biking, cycling, and rock climbing, also contribute to this statistic.

Common dentoalveolar injuries seen in athletes include tooth avulsion, fractures, subluxation, and intrusion, all of which show significant prevalence in recent studies. Jaw and mouth injuries are not uncommon in these activities, further emphasizing the need for preventive measures. To reduce the impact of such injuries, the use of protective gear, such as mouthguards, is strongly recommended for contact sports athletes.²

Oral injuries are significantly more common among athletes who do not wear mouthguards. The reluctance to use mouthguards is often attributed to issues such as difficulty in breathing and speaking, bad breath, xerostomia, nausea, increased costs, or a lack of awareness about the importance of the protective device.³ Greater adoption of mouthguards tends to be associated with sports like martial arts, where facial impacts and collisions are more frequent, highlighting the critical need for this safety measure.⁴

Prevalence of Oral Injuries In Sports

Pasternack JS et al. found that 27% of baseball players experienced orofacial injuries during contact sports. In 2008, Wenli M reported that the prevalence of orofacial injuries among basketball players was 80.6% in professionals and 37.7% in semi-professionals. According to Caglar E et al., 16.6% of football athletes were affected. Galic T et al. observed that handball led to orofacial injuries in 21.8% of athletes. In the same year, Praveena J et al. reported a prevalence rate of 33.8% for hockey players.⁵

A study involving 10-18-year-old Kabaddi players in Delhi-NCR reported a 44.02% prevalence of orofacial injuries. The most commonly affected area was the orbit (26.67%).⁶

Research conducted by Savreen et al. revealed that among schoolchildren aged 6 to 16 years in Amritsar found that 20.20% had experienced dental trauma while playing sports. Notably, 68% of these children had never used mouthguards, highlighting a gap in preventive measures.⁷

Mojarad F reported that the most commonly affected age group for orofacial injuries is 12 years old, with a prevalence of 38.2%. The distribution of injuries across various sports, in descending order, is as follows: handball (16.4%), boxing (16.4%), wrestling (14.5%), baseball (12.7%), soccer (10.9%), judo (9.1%), volleyball (9.1%), taekwondo (5.5%), gymnastics (3.6%), and karate (1.8%).⁸

Impact of Oral Injuries

Malocclusions can predispose individuals to a higher risk of dental injuries, especially during sports or physical activities. The types

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of malocclusions that are particularly prone to injuries include:²

- Increased Overjet (Class II, Division 1 Malocclusion): More exposed and vulnerable to direct trauma, leading to fractures, avulsion, or displacement of upper front teeth.
- Open bite : Lack of protection from the lower teeth increases the likelihood of trauma to the anterior teeth, especially in falls or impacts.
- Deep bite : The lower teeth and surrounding soft tissues are more injury prone.
- Crowding : More susceptible to indirect trauma, such as fractures or root damage, due to uneven force distribution during impact.
- Crossbite : Increased risk of injury to the supporting structures.
- Edge-to- edge bite : Higher risk of chipping, fractures, and enamel wear during trauma.
- Spacing & midline diastema : Exposed teeth are more prone to trauma due to less protection from adjacent teeth.
- Class III malocclusion: Lower teeth are more exposed to impact.

Role of Orthodontics In Sports

Orthodontic patients who participate in contact sports are at a heightened risk of sustaining various oral injuries, ranging from minor to severe. Orthodontics other than treating existing malocclusion plays a vital role in sports dentistry, offering solutions to prevent injuries and protect athletes' smiles by treating malocclusions prone to injuries.¹

Orthodontics plays a crucial role in the health and performance of athletes, particularly when it comes to preventing injuries, enhancing performance, and safeguarding young athletes during their early involvement in sports.

1. Treating Malocclusions Prone to Injuries : Athletes with untreated malocclusions, or misalignments of the teeth and jaws, are more susceptible to facial injuries, particularly during contact sports. Orthodontic treatment can correct these malocclusions, helping to minimize the risk of injury by ensuring that the bite is aligned, reducing the likelihood of trauma to the teeth and jaw during high-impact activities.
2. Addressing Functional and Parafunctional Conditions: Orthodontists also play a key role in treating functional and parafunctional conditions, such as teeth grinding (bruxism) or jaw clenching, which are often exacerbated by the stress of athletic performance. By correcting these conditions, orthodontic intervention not only helps in preventing further dental complications but can also enhance an athlete's overall performance. A properly aligned bite can lead to improved efficiency in breathing, speaking, and eating—all of which contribute to better focus and physical performance on the field.
3. Protecting Young Athletes in Early Stages of Sport Participation : Many young athletes begin their sports journey at an early age. For those already undergoing orthodontic treatment, there's an added concern of protecting the dental and jaw structures during these formative years. The orthodontist's role extends beyond treatment to providing protective

devices such as mouthguards, ensuring that the orthodontic work is safeguarded from potential injuries. These protective measures are especially important as young athletes are at higher risk of sustaining trauma to the face due to the intensity of sports activities.

Dental Injuries Common In Sports

Some of the most common injuries faced by orthodontic patients in sports include:

- Lacerations to the cheeks, lips, and tongue: A stray elbow or blow to the face can cause cuts to the lips, gums, or cheeks. When braces are involved, these injuries can become more severe due to the sharp edges of the orthodontic appliances. Mild cuts can often be managed by rinsing with salt water, but more severe cases may require emergency medical attention.
- Chipped or broken teeth : Minor chipping affects only the enamel, impacting aesthetics but typically causing no pain. However, cracks that extend deeper into the dentin, pulp, or root can lead to significant sensitivity and intense pain, requiring prompt dental intervention.
- These risks highlight the importance of protective measures, such as wearing custom-fitted mouthguards, for orthodontic patients engaged in sports activities.

Different Orthodontic Appliances For Athletes

Athletes use various orthodontic appliances depending on their treatment needs, lifestyle, and level of physical activity. These appliances are designed to align teeth while minimizing risks associated with sports participation.

Fixed appliances, such as metal and ceramic braces, are durable but require careful management to avoid damage during sports, while self-ligating braces reduce maintenance needs. Lingual braces, placed on the inner surfaces of teeth, provide a discreet option and reduce the risk of external trauma.

Retention appliances, including removable or fixed retainers, are used post-treatment to maintain alignment and can be paired with mouthguards for added protection.

Clear aligners, like Invisalign, are popular among athletes as they are removable and less likely to interfere with sports activities. For athletes, clear aligners paired with custom mouthguards often emerge as the preferred option due to their removability, aesthetic appeal, and compatibility with protective measures.

One of the most common option is mouthguards. A mouthguard is a protective device typically worn on the maxilla so as to minimize any risk of injuries to the teeth, jaws, and surrounding soft tissues. It is essential for preventing dental and orofacial injuries and thereby, is strongly recommended for sports that pose a risk of trauma to the teeth and related structures.⁹

Mouthguards function by absorbing the energy generated at the impact site and dispersing the remaining energy across surrounding tissues. They shield the tongue, lips, and cheeks from lacerations caused by the sharp edges of teeth and help prevent angle and condylar fractures by providing support to the mandible.¹⁰

Types of Mouthguards

Custom-fitted laminated mouthguards provide superior protection to orofacial structures in comparison to other varieties, including boil-and-bite mouthguards. Occlusal stability, a better adaptability,¹¹ and greater protection, is seen to be offered with only 25%-50% thinning during its fabrication. The increased thickness of the material allows for enhanced energy absorption, making them more effective in preventing injuries.¹⁰

Boil-and-bite¹ mouthguards are least recommended for any level of sports due to their tendency to dislodge during activity, potentially obstructing the airway.¹² In comparison to custom-fitted mouthguards, boil-and-bite options have an inferior fit, often causing discomfort, looseness, and even nausea.¹³ They do not offer customization with denser material to suit for particular sports and are more prone to deformation due to the reduced heat used in their molding process.⁹ Additionally, they experience significant thinning during fabrication, with a reduction of 70%-99%, giving athletes a false sense of security due to the substantial loss of protective thickness.¹⁴

Polyolefin materials hold great potential due to their increased shock absorption and reduced water absorption compared to ethylene vinyl acetate. Additionally, they provide a prolonged working time, allowing more time for precise intraoral fitting.¹⁵

Design of Mouthguards

The design and construction of mouthguards should include the following specifications:

1. Coverage should extend to the distal side of the maxillary first permanent molar, with recommended thicknesses of 3 mm on the labial/buccal surface, 3 mm on the occlusal surfaces, and 2 mm on the palatal/lingual surface.^{16,17}
2. Bilateral and balanced occlusion for optimal fit and function.¹⁸
3. Athletes participating in any sport with a risk of dental or facial trauma, like rugby, football, kickboxing, boxing, taekwondo, basketball, and sports like ice hockey, field hockey, and lacrosse, should use laminated custom-fitted mouthguards.⁹
4. Wearing instructions : These mouthguards should be worn not only during competitions and games but also during training sessions.

Impact of Wearing Mouthguards

A custom-fitted laminated mouthguard with a minimum thickness of 3 mm is highly effective in reducing impact forces to the teeth, outperforming over-the-counter mouthguards.⁹ Clenching while wearing a mouthguard further enhances its ability to absorb impact.¹⁹ There has been no significant difference in the reduction of impact forces to the head, irrespective of whether a mouthguard is worn or not.

Use of a mouthguard does affect stomatognathic function that is related to static or dynamic balance in postural control. A positive correlation has been established between biting force level, increased limb muscle activity and neurophysiologic excitability that contributes to postural stabilization and joint fixation.⁹

Conclusion

Participation in sports activities poses a significant risk of dental and facial injuries, making protection a critical component of an athlete's safety. Orthodontic patients, in particular, require special attention to safeguard their smiles during physical activity. The use of properly designed and custom-fitted mouthguards has proven to be the most effective way to prevent trauma to the teeth, jaws, and soft tissues, ensuring preservation of both function and aesthetics. By promoting awareness and advocating for the consistent use of protective gear, including during training sessions, orthodontists and sports professionals can play a vital role in protecting smiles on the field and fostering a culture of safety in sports.

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